

BEACON: A Lunar South Pole Joint Technology Demonstration Mission. M. Cross¹, A. Higginson¹, S. Monger¹, N. Thiyagarajan¹, C. Dubois¹, M. Pitropov¹, B. Bonham-Carter¹, H. Burd¹, L. Chavier¹, A. Pascual¹, S. Villemure¹, I. Abcarius¹, G. O’Shea¹, T. Heydrich¹, A. Budhkar¹, R. Rogers¹, A. J. Macdonald¹, K. Mewhort¹, T. Farley¹, J. Enns¹, S. Pillay¹, Y. Brown¹, M. Faragalli¹, ¹Mission Control, 162 Elm St W, Ottawa, K1R 6N5 Canada

Introduction: Mission Control and Astrobotic Technology, Inc. are collaborating on a joint lunar rover mission demonstration known as BEACON (Benchmark for Engineering and Autonomous Capabilities in Operations and Navigation). The mission will integrate Astrobotic’s CubeRover® mobility platform with Mission Control’s Spacefarer™ mission operations software. CubeRover will be delivered to the lunar south polar region aboard Astrobotic’s Griffin-1 lander, scheduled for launch no earlier than July 2026. Once deployed, rover operations will be jointly conducted from Astrobotic’s facilities in Pittsburgh and Mission Control’s facilities in Ottawa. The collaboration aims to showcase how commercial partnerships can accelerate advancements in lunar exploration technologies.

Figure 1: Development and engineering model of CubeRover have been operated in Mission Control’s Moonyard as part of hardware-in-the-analogue-environment-in-the-loop testing for Spacefarer™ custom application development.

Mission Objective and Profile: BEACON’s primary objective is to demonstrate CubeRover’s performance on the lunar surface and validate Spacefarer™ as a capable ground-operations platform. After deployment and egress from the Griffin lander, CubeRover will undergo up to 120 hours of surface operations near Nobile Crater. During this phase, the joint operations team will execute mobility tests, including driving in shadowed regions, and collect imagery for AI model retraining and panoramic stitching. Initial drive segments will establish baseline performance metrics that will be compared against several experimental operational modes. Figure 2 shows a high-level concept for the joint surface operations and demonstration activities.

Figure 2: High-level mission overview to represent major elements of the joint mission that will last up to 120 hours.

These advanced operational modes include semi-autonomous navigation, VR-based teleoperation, and hazard assessment powered by the rover’s onboard AI payload. Together, they will be used for the remainder of the mission to evaluate novel methods for efficient and safe rover control. Mission Control’s contributions focus on demonstrating cutting-edge operator tools within Spacefarer™ (an example operator console layout shown in Figure 3) and validating technologies that support future autonomous and human-directed lunar missions.

Figure 3: Example of Spacefarer™ operator console that includes the command builder, data explorer, and image viewers of both front and back cameras.

Technology Demonstrations: The technology demonstration showcases how Astrobotic and Mission Control are using the Spacefarer™ mission operations platform to command and control CubeRover during lunar surface operations. Spacefarer’s Common Operating Picture (COP) and Live Planning tools provide operators with synchronized 3D visualization, imagery integration, and waypoint-based planning both through a web interface and virtual reality. These tools enable operators to visualize rover pose, review images linked to location data, plan traverses interactively, and iterate seamlessly between planning and situational awareness. Semi-autonomous navigation reduces operator workload by automatically generating and sequenc-

ing complex command stacks, breaking long traverses into safe, reviewable segments and enforcing multi-operator approval for uplink.

To support localization on a rover without onboard navigation sensors, Mission Control developed a georeferencing application that allows operators to refine the rover’s position by selecting tie points across images in Spacefarer™. Using camera models, rover pose estimates, and a ground-plane assumption, the system computes survey points and updates the rover’s world-frame position after each drive step, with error reduction techniques such as RANSAC improving reliability. While this operator-assisted localization is inherently approximate, testing shows it is sufficiently accurate for short drive steps and effectively supports mission objectives by compensating for wheel slip and other accumulated errors.

An onboard AI payload enables real-time hazard assessment by running neural-network inference on images captured during rover operations. Activated by ground controllers and constrained by power availability, the system generates two key outputs for each image: segmentation masks and an overall hazard assessment. One model identifies lighting hazards such as darkness or saturation, while another detects terrain features including regolith, rocks, sky, and spacecraft components. These results, along with an estimated distance to the nearest hazard, are downlinked and visualized in Mission Control’s Spacefarer™ platform, an example shown in Figure 4, where segmentation overlays enhance situational awareness.

Figure 4: Ground segment visualization of classes from the onboard AI software payload data product. Green represents the ‘sky’, red represents ‘spacecraft’ elements (CubeRover’s wheels), orange represents ‘rocks’, and blue represents ‘regolith’.

To support this capability, Mission Control developed a machine-learning pipeline centered on data curation, model training, and flight-ready deployment. Training used a mix of public lunar imagery and private datasets from the Moonyard analogue site, with careful attention to camera representativeness and the domain gap between Earth analogues and lunar south-pole lighting conditions.

Validated models underwent hardware-in-the-loop testing on CubeRover’s development platform and were integrated with NASA’s core Flight System for autonomous operation. Because no real imagery from the landing site existed during development, the system was architected to allow in-mission model updates, enabling adaptation as new data becomes available despite the inherent operational risks and bandwidth limitations.

Conclusion: The BEACON mission will serve as a milestone in advancing commercial lunar mobility and mission operations, demonstrating how Astrobotic’s CubeRover and Mission Control’s Spacefarer™ platform can jointly deliver productive surface operations. By validating semi-autonomous navigation, real-time hazard assessment, adaptive onboard AI models, and distributed mission control tools, BEACON establishes operational heritage for future lunar and planetary missions, particularly those targeting challenging environments such as the lunar south pole. Its results lay the groundwork for more intelligent, flexible, and collaborative robotic systems capable of longer-duration operations, complex traverses, and coordinated multi-asset deployments. Ultimately, BEACON highlights the growing role of commercial innovation and autonomy in shaping sustainable, high-efficiency exploration of the Moon and beyond.

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